

Eating and Drinking
in the Ancient Near East

Proceedings of the 67th Rencontre Assyriologique
Internationale, Turin, July 12–16, 2021

Edited by Stefano de Martino,
Elena Devecchi and Maurizio Viano

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The Assyrian Royal Banquet

A Sociological and Anthropological Approach

Ludovico Portuese*

This paper explores the Assyrian royal banquet through a sociological and anthropological analysis of the extant visual evidence from the first millennium BCE. It focuses specifically on the immaterial aspects of commensality (hierarchies, positions, gestures, etiquette, proxemic, hygiene), the study of which reveals that these contributed to the integrity of a culture and the evolutionary success of the group.

1. Introduction

As observed by Georg Simmel, eating and drinking are primitive, individual, and egotistical physiological facts. Further, as such they are shared by virtue of being essentially common activities. Commensality, or the practice of eating and drinking together, and its sociological structure is thus a spontaneous and direct fact of nature; an act of selfishness, primitiveness, and universal material interest is turned into an occasion of “immeasurable sociological significance”.¹ In a nutshell, the very naturalness and primitiveness of eating and drinking is what makes it so fundamentally social.

Although studied throughout anthropology and sociology, as well as in the social sciences and the humanities, the social functions of commensality, as a cross-cultural and transhistorical phenomenon, vary greatly from culture to culture.² The etymological history of the word suggests its complexity: commensality may imply the sharing of food and drink (*com-mensalis*), but also the sharing of a table, a place, or a moment (*com-mensa*), or alternatively the costs of a meal

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¹ Simmel, 1997: 130.

² For an examination of the importance of commensality, with a specific view on the ancient Near East, see the contributions in Pollock, 2012 and, with a special focus on Mesopotamia in the first millennium BCE, see Ermidoro, 2015: 39–43.

(*commensalia*).³ Either way, the word commensality always recalls a material dimension, above all the table (*mensa*), the utensils of the meal, the spatial context where the food and drink are consumed, and the financial contribution to the meal. However, commensality also involves some immaterial aspects which are directly linked to the participants, the way in which they interact with each other, the setting (both physical and psychological), the food and the drink, and in turn the ways that material aspects influence and are influenced by immaterial ones. Commensality is an example of the existence of behavioural rules, of prescribed gestures and manners that regulate the consumption of the repast or the content of conversations, and that govern the hierarchical organization of banqueters and their movements. Although the immaterial dimensions of commensality may be hidden or not stated explicitly, they are fundamental 1) in creating and reinforcing social bonds, and 2) in generating a sense of belonging to the same community in order to preserve it. It is exactly these two aspects that I would like to outline in this paper through the analysis of some immaterial dimensions which the representation of first-millennium Assyrian royal banquets, I believe, strives to display, and which sociology and anthropology may help to reveal.⁴

Artists in the Assyrian period elevate an event of physiological primitiveness into the sphere of social interaction. Being represented with specific inner artistic organizations, the external act of feeding and drinking becomes a sociological matter and, to quote Simmel, “arranges itself in a more aesthetic, stylized and supra-individually regulated form”.⁵ The best visual evidence of a banquet at the court of the Assyrian king comes from an Assyrian ivory plaque from Fort Shalmaneser at Kalhu (Fig. 1) and the reliefs of rooms 2 and 7 (Fig. 2) in the royal palace of Sargon II at Dur-Sharrukin.⁶ In the main scene, the Assyrian royal banquet is basically portrayed through groups of seated banqueters who face each other across a table with foodstuff, raise beakers to drink or make a toast, and who are surrounded by standing attendants.⁷ The king is apparently absent from the palace reliefs, although he must have been represented somewhere, as in the ivory plaque from Kalhu.⁸

³ Jönsson *et al.*, 2021: 1–2.

⁴ For an anthropological approach to banquet in Assyria, see Ermidoro, 2015.

⁵ Simmel, 1997: 131.

⁶ For the entire sequence of reliefs from Sargon II's royal palace, see Botta / Flandin, 1849: pls. 52–76, 107–114.

⁷ There seems to be no foodstuff on the tables of the ivory plaque. Moreover, one person is depicted in the act of receiving an object (food? handkerchief?) from an attendant and is not drinking. For a detailed description of these images, see Albenda, 1986: 80–82. For an analysis of the scenes and their significance, see Matthiae, 2012; Winter, 2016; Ermidoro, 2015: 227–228; Portuese, 2020: 81–86, 175–176.

⁸ Reade, 1979: 81; Winter, 2016: 43.

As already pointed out, these banquet scenes, perhaps including the ivory plaque, must probably be considered as a direct and positive consequence of specific activities, such as the war and the hunt depicted in the lower registers of rooms 2 and 7.⁹ Thus, they probably do not represent daily meals, but exceptional episodes which were likely organized in the royal palace to celebrate and commemorate a specific event. Now, as observed by Claude Grignon, commensality is a manifestation of pre-existing social groups, whose differences and classifications can be based on age, gender, and ethnic identity, or on voluntary associations of a political and/or religious nature.¹⁰

Fig. 1: Assyrian ivory plaque, Kalhu, Fort Shalmaneser (Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York 59.107.22; Drawing by Steve K. Simons – Panoply Vase Animation Project for GALATEO project).

Fig. 2: Relief 17, Room 2, Sargon II's Royal Palace, Dur-Sharrukin (Botta / Flandin, 1849: pl. 64).

⁹ Matthiae, 2012: 482–483; Winter, 2016.

¹⁰ Grignon, 2001: 24.

To borrow Grignon's terminology, the type of commensality which is discussed in this scene can be described, first, as *exceptional*, because it celebrates a memorable event (war, hunt) that did not take place each day, and, second, as *institutional*, because of its hierarchical nature and the presence of a ruler of the institution, the Assyrian king, who sponsored the banquet.¹¹ Since access to the royal building and to particular inner spaces where banquets probably took place was regularly controlled and those who maintained access to such places were carefully selected, the banqueters depicted as sharing the king's table must have been selected and privileged guests.¹² In this regard, I am tempted to define the representation of the Assyrian royal banquet according to what Grignon calls *segregative* commensality. This term denotes a further expression of institutional commensality which is usually found in hierarchised societies to set up or restore the group by closing it, thereby strengthening a "We" by pointing out and rejecting, as symbols of otherness, the "not We".¹³ The immaterial dimensions "depicted" on the Assyrian royal banquet scenes comply with a commensality that was exceptional, institutional and segregative in essence.

2. Setting the tables

Furthermore, the arrangement of tables and the position of the banqueters is not accidental but complies with specific social needs which are dictated by the above-described type of commensality. In this regard, it should be noted that semi-fixed features, such as chairs and tables, are not already laid out in the room but are brought into a room which appears empty at the moment of the repast. This is confirmed not only by the reliefs of the façade of room 2 at Dur-Sharukin,¹⁴ but also by an Assyrian banquet protocol which describes how, at the beginning of the dinner, when the king enters the room with his magnates, "the table and] the couch for the king [are place]d opposite the doorway". Also, at the end of the dinner the magnates "rise and remain standing. The tables of the crown prince and of the magnates are lifted up. The table of the crown prince and the table before the king are *set in motion*."¹⁵ This suggests that there may have been a hierarchical order in which both the furniture and banqueters were arranged. Moreover, such use of moveable furniture allowed protocol-holders to lay out the tables and chairs according to special and new needs deriving from political and social changes. In this connection, the notion that the king was not of equal status with the other participants is reinforced visually on the Kalhu ivory plaque, where

¹¹ Grignon, 2001: 26.

¹² Portuese, 2020.

¹³ Grignon, 2001: 28–29.

¹⁴ Botta / Flandin, 1849: pls. 10–23; see also pl. 30.

¹⁵ SAA 20 33: i 2 – i 3, r i 50 – r i 52. For an-in-depth examination of this text, see Ermidoro, 2015: 161–189.

he is seated apart and is distinguished by his high-backed seat, dress, size, and paraphernalia. Similarly, on the same plaque the figure immediately in front of the king is visually differentiated by his position and the diadem he wears, which has ribbons attached to it and is a marker of the crown prince.¹⁶ This suggests that tables closer to the king's table were occupied by the most important and trusted persons by the king: the closer that one was to the king's table, the more important was his position within the Assyrian court hierarchy. Moreover, it is likely that each table represented a specific rank of officials. Notwithstanding such a hierarchical organization, a remarkable cohesiveness can be highlighted from the position and arrangement of the banqueters.

From an anthropological perspective, we are informed that a setting can offer many types of behavioural opportunities which may facilitate or hinder social behaviour. The design of a space and its semi-fixed features can dramatically alter these social affordances relative to the occupants who are disposed to use it. In this respect, the terms *sociopetal* and *sociofugal* are environmental psychological concepts used to denote such designs.¹⁷ The basic difference between them lies in the fact that these contrasting social settings facilitate (*sociopetal*) or inhibit (*sociofugal*) social interaction. Thus, a sociopetal room tends to bring people together and affords interaction by orienting occupants toward each other, whereas a sociofugal space may have boundary walls and seats which face away from each other and it tends to discourage meetings or conversations between individuals, thereby inhibiting interaction (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: An example of a sociofugal (left) and sociopetal (right) setting, respectively (Meagher / Marsh, 2017: fig. 1).

¹⁶ Winter, 2016: 52; Portuese, 2020: 71.

¹⁷ Osmond, 1957; Sommer, 1967. See also Hall, 1966: 108–111. More recently, see Meagher / Marsh, 2017.

The proportion of the room length to width, the furniture arrangement, and the furniture density all constitute the primary variables which affect social interaction and reflect the operational definition of sociopetality and sociofugality. The physical setting of the Assyrian banquet imagery is unknown, but it is likely that room 2 and similar oblong rooms may have been the physical venue for such meetings.¹⁸ Tables could be set in line along this room, but they could have been also placed side by side. In either case, what we see in the banquet scenes is a setting closer to a sociopetal arrangement (Fig. 4), the aim being to facilitate and promote interaction between banqueters.

Fig. 4: The sociopetal setting of the Assyrian royal banquet (Botta / Flandin, 1849: pl. 64; drawing by author).

Such a sociopetal space greatly impacts on a number of sensorial inputs and aspects that cannot be explained by reliefs or texts. Sight, olfaction, sound, smell, and one's feel of one's neighbours' breath all combine to signal unmistakable involvement with another body. This arrangement allows the sensation of warmth from the body of the nearby banqueter to create an intimate space. We can imagine that the smell of freshly washed hair and the blurring of another person's features seen close up combine with the sensation of warmth to create intimacy. Thighs and elbows are brought into contact, hands can reach and grasp extremities, and so one is able to hold or grasp the other person. All these aspects were created deliberately by the arrangement of the furniture, with the distance between banqueters perhaps ranging between intimate (0–50 cm) and personal (0.5–1.2 m), according to Edward Hall's categorisations.¹⁹ Personal distance, in particular, is the limit of physical domination in a very real sense. Beyond it, a person cannot

¹⁸ For the floorplan, see Portuese, 2020: fig. 11.

¹⁹ Hall, 1966: 113–129.

easily “get his hands on” someone else.²⁰ Such an intimacy between banqueters and their arrangement in units of four individuals per table suggests that this was a way to activate and tighten internal solidarity within specific micro-groups. Instead, it is likely that the king was seated at a social distance (1.2–3.5 m), where intimate visual details in the face were not perceived, and nobody could touch the king unless some special effort was taken. At this distance, nonetheless, voice level may be normal, and conversations could be conducted at a normal level.

3. Etiquette and hygiene

The strong feeling of closeness and intimacy also seems to be expressed through minute instances of etiquette, whose regulation is a result of the socialization of the meal. All the banqueters, including the king, are equated by posture and gesture. The erect posture, which seems conventional for Assyrians according to the Assyrian visual evidence, was considered to carry positive connotations of appearing agreeable, while holding the head high indicated correctness and dignity.²¹ Moreover, this posture was an element which expressed reciprocity because it implied direct eye-contact between banqueters. One gesture which both banqueters and the king himself perform is the raising of their beakers. We don't actually know why the act of drinking was chosen to “freeze” the repast and thus whether it stood for a subset or extension of food.²² In any event, what emerges is that such a gesture diminishes the differences between banqueters, since raising beakers may have meant that men are toasting one other and this very scene of *conviviality* made the partakers similar in status.²³ Moreover, it is interesting to note that each banqueter balances a bowl or beaker in one hand, making use of all his fingertips. In this respect, one may suspect that a toasting etiquette may have existed – as is described in Xenophon's *Cyropaedia* in referring to the Medes – but was perhaps known only to higher-status guests.²⁴ In this connection, special mention needs to be made of Sargon II's reliefs, whose material dimension of commensality is represented by the lion-headed cups (called in texts *kaqqad nēšē* and probably made of silver, bronze, or even gold) which all banqueters held to drink wine.²⁵ This particular beaker is also attested in divine banquets and rituals

²⁰ Hall, 1966: 120.

²¹ Cifarelli, 1998: 215; Portuese, 2020: 111.

²² For a selection of reasons from earlier studies on why the drinking act metonymically stands for the banquet itself, see Portuese / Scalisi, 2021: 137–142. For an anthropological approach to drinking alcoholic beverages, see Dietler, 1990.

²³ The term *conviviality* further complicates or enriches the notion of commensality, since it focuses on the friendly and enjoyable aspect of being together (Jönsson *et al.*, 2021: 2).

²⁴ Portuese / Scalisi, 2021: 140–141.

²⁵ Gaspa, 2014: 25–33.

performed within temples, which is a further indicator of its special status.²⁶ This implies that, by being involved in a lay banquet and being proffered to guests, the object was highly significant, marking the event as very exceptional and, since it was held by all banqueters, an egalitarian symbol. Although it is expected that in similar circumstances the king proffered to his guests delicate kinds of vessels and fine pieces of furniture, the lion-headed cup held in the hands of the banqueters turns the event into a very special occasion. In fact, the use of special objects together with the presence of music (on relief 21, room 2) leads me to adopt another term from anthropology to describe the Sargonid banquets, namely the notion of *feast*. The feast is defined as an event that involves “some combination of elements including exotic foods often prepared and served in special vessels”, that “may be held in special locations” and involves “symbolically charged practices that differentiate and privilege feasting from other meals”.²⁷ This term expands and adds value to the definition of commensality, and can be used in this context for other aspects as well. In fact, Sargon II’s feasting is made unique not only by special or splendid meals or dining objects or the location, but also by the presence of splendid company: those different Assyrian high-ranking officials (themselves distinguished by garments) whom the king eats with is as important as what he eats and what he eats on and from. But the uniqueness of the event does not imply that feasting was itself a rare phenomenon. As noted by Joan M. Gero, feasting should rather be seen “as a regularly occurring social practice, one that is involved and evoked at many points in the intensification of power relations between rulers and ruled. Feasts generally seek to accomplish the shared participation of persons of different ranks, and these persons are brought together in a single setting that intensifies the very socio-political divides that it also bridges and subverts”.²⁸ This means that the feasts which we see celebrated on Sargon II’s reliefs were powerful tools, both in reality and as visual messages, which were used by the king to define relationships and boundaries, and thereby unite and divide at the same time. Social distinctions were thus affirmed through the performance of feasts.²⁹

Finally, although I do not wish to venture into a debate that would require a focused analysis, I would like to point out that the rules of appropriate behaviour may be justified by their basis in commonly held moral principles and ideals, perhaps deriving from a military context.³⁰ Conventions which govern the act of drinking or the stances which are maintained at the king’s table should not be

²⁶ Gaspa, 2014: 29; Ermidoro, 2015: 228. On the provenance and related meaning of the lion-headed cups depicted on Sargon II’s reliefs, see Stronach, 1996: 186–191; Gaspa, 2014: 30–33; Gunter, 2020: 149–156, and earlier bibliography in Portuese, 2020: 76.

²⁷ Joyce, 2010: 225.

²⁸ Gero, 2003: 286.

²⁹ Dietler, 2001: 77–78.

³⁰ Cifarelli, 1998: 215.

considered as colourless formal aspects which are represented passively by the artist. Rather, I suspect that these conventions reflected rules, practices, and norms for behaviour that bonded participants to behave in certain ways and created a structure in which banqueters could collectively participate in potentially morally transformative activities. In a nutshell, I assume that there must have been a strict correlation, as already asserted by some philosophers, between what we today call manners/etiquette rules and morality, which perhaps derived from a basically martial context.³¹

In association with these aspects and the system of a minutely codified etiquette, at least in its most ceremonious and official aspects, this process of formal selection and the cohesiveness of banqueters is complemented by another immaterial dimension, that of hygiene. By hygiene I refer to the basic dictionary definition, which is understood as the “conditions or practices (as of cleanliness) conducive to health”.³² Such a definition applies naturally to the Assyrian world, where there seems to have been great awareness of good hygiene practices and their role in reducing the spread of disease. The already-quoted Assyrian banquet protocol text reveals the high levels of hygiene which existed in the banquet environment in its reference to the frequent proffering of napkins and handkerchiefs,³³ and especially to the container of hand-water (*hašbu ša mē*), which was constantly supervised by a special lackey.³⁴ In such a context, the use of water should not be conceived as a means to reach cultic purity but to prevent the spread of diseases. In fact, a correlation between illness and clean water is often emphasised in Assyrian letters.³⁵ In addition, it seems that the proffering of good water even to deportees reflected a kind of attention and care of the king towards his people.³⁶ By contrast, the inaccessibility to good and clean water led to a lack of good hygiene and implied a kind of social ostracism.³⁷ Not having access to good water and cleanliness meant becoming ill. This in turn was probably perceived as the loss of the king’s support. This aspect complies with the typical forms of segregative commensality, where there is a remarkable necessity for the group’s individuals (“We”) to preserve their “purity” by protecting their bodies and the food they consume from the stain and untoward pollutions which others (“not We”) may inflict.

*

³¹ See, in particular, Buss, 1999; Stohr, 2012; 2018.

³² <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/hygiene>.

³³ SAA 20 33: ii 16 – ii 19.

³⁴ SAA 20 33: ii 20 – ii 21.

³⁵ SAA 10 318; SAA 19 22: r 16 – r 22.

³⁶ SAA 1 247.

³⁷ SAA 18 181: 19–22.

In conclusion, what emerges from this brief analysis of the immaterial aspects of commensality is that, both in reality and in iconography, there was an effort to implement and represent those strategies that were carefully chosen to preserve the integrity of a very small group of people. These strategies contributed towards the evolutionary success of that group. Through the primitive origins of commensality, a society is somehow formed and held together: sharing and incorporating food implies the incorporation of the partaker into the community and simultaneously defines his or her place within it. In this regard, Pasi Falk highlights the bidirectional value of the eating mouth, both in incorporating the food of the community into one's body and "being eaten into the community".³⁸ This bond is created primarily by sharing. However, I would emphasise that, especially within an institutional and segregative form of commensality which exists to celebrate a common success or exceptional event, more immaterial aspects work in tandem with the material ones in order to incorporate or "eat" partakers into the community and thereby forge, reinforce, and protect the integrity of a single group, at the same time defining the place occupied by each individual within the same group. Socially speaking, the members of Assyrian royal society were what they ate.

Abbreviations

- SAA 1 see Parpola, 1987.
 SAA 10 see Parpola, 1993.
 SAA 18 see Reynolds, 2003.
 SAA 19 see Luukko, 2012.
 SAA 20 see Parpola, 2017.

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